
PRELIMINARY EVALUATION OF LEAP MOTION CONTROLLER AS A HUMAN TREMOR RECORD DEVICE

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Abstract

The Leap Motion Controller is a device for hand gesture controlled user interfaces with sub-millimeter accuracy. However, up to this point its capabilities under some light conditions and different distances between controller and hand in a static scenario have not been analyzed. Therefore, this paper presents a preliminary study of a Leap Motion Controller. The main focus is to describe the typical controller behavior. For this evaluation, a static plaster hand model was used as a reference object. For static configuration, the deviation found between each measured 3D position and the average measured position was below 0.78 mm.

Author Keywords: leap motion controller; accuracy; measurement precision

Introduction

Tremor is defined as an involuntary and approximately rhythmic movement of muscles. There are many ways to measure the human tremor; the most common methods include accelerometry and electromyography (EMG) [5]. In the past few years the different optical sensors, which allow the acquisition of 3D objects, have been developed [2,4]. Concurrently, with the development of new sensors, the number of potential applications vastly increases, especially because of the increased accuracy and robustness of 3D sensors [8] and a drop in prices.

The tremor analysis application has particular requirements such as high accuracy and high precision [5]. These requirements are desired due to the two common tremor parameters, amplitude that can reach small values (around millimeters) and frequency, which can reach up to around 12 Hz [5].

Figure 1. The Cartesian coordinate system used to describe positions in the controller's sensory space.

Figure 2. The setup of the experimental environment.

In this sense, the Leap Motion Controller (LMC) appears as a controller that allows precise and fluid tracking of multiple hands, fingers, and small objects in free space with a sub-millimeter accuracy. The controller's capabilities in realistic environments were analyzed by Weichert [8] and Guna [3]. However, the previous studies do not evaluate the specific hand tracking behavior.

The human tremor analysis field can benefit of use this kind of sensor. Therefore, this paper presents a preliminary evaluation of LMC hand tracking under some light conditions and different distances between controller and hand in a static scenario.

Experimental Design

Depending on the human age, for example, the tremor amplitude varies between $0.4 \text{ mm} \pm 0.2 \text{ mm}$ for young individuals and $1.1 \text{ mm} \pm 0.6 \text{ mm}$ for old individuals [1,7]. The controller's performance was evaluated using a static hand as a reference object, this way, the hand palm position was tracked and recorded to evaluate the dispersion of the results.

Leap Motion Controller

The Leap Motion Controller is a consumer-grade sensor developed by Leap Motion (www.leapmo-

www.leapmotion.com). It is primarily designed for hand gesture and finger position detection in interactive software applications.

The LMC uses infrared (IR) imaging to determine the position of predefined objects in a limited space in real time. Technically, very few details are known about the precise nature of the algorithms used due to patent and trade secret restrictions. However, from inspection of the controller, it is clear that three separate IR LED emitters are used in conjunction with two IR cameras [8]. The controller's field of view is an inverted pyramid centered on the device. The effective range of the controller extends from approximately 25 to 600 millimeters above the device.

The Cartesian coordinate system used to describe positions in the controller's sensory space is shown in Figure 1. It should be noted that the sampling frequency is not stable, it can not be set, and varies significantly [3].

Measurement Setup

The LMC was fixed on a plane and a reference plaster hand model was fixed above the LMC, as shown in Figure 2.

A laptop computer, Intel® Core™ i7-3520M CPU 2.9 GHz with 8 GB of RAM, with the developed evaluation software which is described in [6] were used for real-time data acquisition and logging.

During the measurement of static locations, the hand model was firmly attached using a metal structure (Figure 2). The static measurement was performed under four experimental conditions sets as shown in Table 1.

The measured positions are denoted by $p[i] = (p_x[i], p_y[i], p_z[i]) \in R^3$, where the components $p_x[i]$, $p_y[i]$ and $p_z[i]$ represent the coordinates in the LMC Cartesian coordinate system of the i -th sample ($1 \leq i \leq N, i \in N$) taken at the same position, and N means the total number of samples taken.

	Illumination intensity (lux)*	Distance from controller (cm)
Set 1	353	27
Set 2	72	
Set 3	353	17
Set 4	72	
* Approximately		

Table 1. Predefined experimental conditions sets.

In the following, for each set, at least 2.500 samples were measured. In order to analyze the sensor's accuracy and precision in static scenario the deviation and standard deviation were calculated.

Results

The Figure 3 shows deviation between each measured position and mean value for x- and y-axis from set 2.

Figure 3. Deviation between each measured position and the mean value for x- and y-axis from set 2.

Figure 3 presents one of the smallest deviations for x- and y-axis, which is less than 0.43 mm in the case of x-axis and in the y-axis case, is less than 0.59 mm.

The box-and-whisker plots in Figure 4 the average deviation concerning the x-, y- and z-axis at each set (see Table 1). The boxes are representing the interquartile range that contains 50% of the values and the whiskers are marking the minimum and maximum values, excluding outliers (marked as red points).

Figure 5 shows a comparison of standard deviation of x-, y- and z-axis for each set.

The lowest standard deviation (0.085 mm) was measured on the x-axis 27 cm above the controller and an illumination intensity of 72 lux, while the highest standard deviation (0.57 mm) was measured on the z-axis at the same conditions.

Figure 4. Box-and-whisker plot of x-, y- and z-axis for each set.

Figure 5. Standard deviations of x-, y- and z-axis for each set.

Discussion and Conclusions

In this paper, we have described a preliminary evaluation of the hand tracking performance of the LMC in the static scenario.

In this study, it should be noted that the LMC software version used was 2.2.5 and the Application Programming Interface (API) function used to get the hand position was Hand.palmPosition. Unlike, that information were not clear in Weichert [8] and Guna [3] studies.

The results revealed a significant increase in the standard deviation when the hand model was moved away from the controller’s surface, particularly in the z-axis, which combines with results presented by [3].

In some cases, the controller only tracked the static point for a few seconds and then stopped. The sampling frequency keeps around 58 Hz with small changes (0.5 Hz), which is below the expected value that it was 60 Hz. These two phenomena were also reported in [3].

Concerning about illumination intensity, the set of measurements revealed no significant deviation difference between the sets of 353 lux and 72 lux. Future work will focus on correlation tests to evaluate the best settings for the use of the LMC, and estimating a model of the error probability density function.

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